

Predictive Data Acquisition for Lifelong Visual Teach, Repeat and Learn

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Abstract—Nowadays, robots can operate in environments which are not tailored for them. This allows their deployments in changing and human-populated environments, which recent advances in machine learning methods enabled. The efficiency of these methods is largely determined by the quality of their training data. An up-to-date and well-balanced training dataset is paramount for achieving robust robot operation. To achieve long-term operation, the robot has to deal with perpetual environmental changes, forcing it to keep its models up-to-date. We present an exploration method allowing a mobile robot to gather high-quality data to update its models both while performing its duties and when idle, maximizing effectivity. The robot evaluates the quality of the data gathered in the past and based on that, it creates preferences which influence how often these locations are visited. This exploration method was integrated with a self-supervised visual teach-and-repeat pipeline. We show the precision and robustness of visual-based navigation to improve when using machine-learned models trained by our exploration method. Our research resulted in a robotic navigation system that can not only annotate its training data but also ensure that its training dataset is balanced and up-to-date. The codes, datasets, trained models and examples for our experiments can be found online for better reproducibility at github.com/rouceto1/vtrl.

I. INTRODUCTION

The capability to move from one place to another is essential for any mobile robot. Over the last few years, robot navigation methods have improved significantly through the deployment of machine learning. This impacted mainly the domain of vision-based navigation and localisation. However, machine learning-based navigation methods require vast amounts of training data relevant to a given context. Even in the case of unsupervised or semi-supervised learning, where costly annotation can be avoided, significant time and effort have to be invested in curating the training data. Moreover, as the operational environments are seldom static, the robots have to learn continuously to keep up with the changes in their surroundings. This requires that a robot not only gathers data opportunistically during its routine operation but also actively explores the environment to obtain new and diverse training data. Then, it should use these data to refine its learned models, improving its navigation efficiency and robustness over time.

Analogically, robot has to check if the environment it navigates changes so it can effectively pass. Some apparent strategies are to check every path randomly or check all equally. Since not all environments change at the same rate, it can be beneficial to estimate which place or information is

This work was supported by the Grant Agency of the Czech Technical University in Prague, grant No. SGS22/168/OHK3/3T/13 and by project ROBOPROX no. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004590 funded by the EU.

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Digital Object Identifier (DOI): see top of this page.

Figure 1: Visualization of internal **timetable** that is crated using **preferences** p_i . Green cells represent chosen time slots; orange represents time slots forced by the robot’s mission. The percentage of time slots used either by exploration or exploitation from each line is **uptime** when the robot can drive. The columns represent each group of information to be gathered, and here, they represent places where the robot goes. The maximum information gathered per time window is represented by **duty cycle** and represents how many of these can be visited. From the timetable, an **ambiguity** is computed for each information category using some **methods**. This together with past p_i is then again used to make p_{i+1} .

least known to the robot/algorithm and needs to be seen more often. Most of the deployed robots do run in environments that change over time. Some operate during the day/night cycle, and others operate in forests where the trees grow or are cut. These changes should not only be compensated for but also learned from. If the robot uses only a camera feed for navigation, the changes can be profound, especially considering glare or shadows, and it needs to know the representation of both. Due to hardware limitations, there are currently no mobile robots on the market that can operate with 100% uptime. Realistically, the robot has to dock, charge itself, offload data and undergo maintenance at minimum. Currently, the battery technology alone allows an uptime of 50% in ideal conditions, as stated for SPOT robots [1] or even less for other platforms such as Clearpath Husky [2]. Due to these constraints, the robot has limited time to fulfil its given mission; therefore, it can only collect some data about the environment and has to choose what it will gather carefully.

A robot, that needs to capture all information in a changing environment should be able to select its timetable when it wants to explore the environment. This timetable should represent the robot’s ability to acquire important data from

the environment. Robot has to be able to decide where to go or which information to acquire, it also needs to be able to assess the quality of each known information it has already seen. To do so, it needs apply some **metrics** to calculate which information is the most important.

In the next section, we describe the current state of research in this field. Later, we introduce our system seen in Fig. 1 and the principles needed to replicate our results. Finally, we compare our system to previous work and lay the ground for some more questions that need to be answered in future work.

II. RELATED WORK

Visual teach and repeat (VTR) navigation is a concept in robotics which splits the deployment into two phases. First, while a human operator drives the robot, it stores data from the camera and its inputs. In the second repeat phase, the input commands are then replayed, and the original camera image is compared to the current live feed from its cameras, which enables the robot to correct its heading error that is accumulated by slippage and/or imperfect replay of the internal commands. It has been deployed to UAVs as well as on ground robots [3]. It has been mathematically proven that for most trajectories, this approach converges to the original path by correcting for horizontal displacement between the images [4]. This has been studied thoroughly under various settings [5], [6].

An important feature of the VTR systems is its robustness in long-term missions. However, most systems had to address environmental changes during the deployment, which can happen slowly over several runs. The first methods addressed mainly shadows using photogrammetric methods [7], which did not translate to indoors where the light was not sun-dependent. Another approach was to learn feature descriptors that are conditions invariant both indoors and outdoors [8], [9]. In [10], the authors combined both the photogrammetry and the features to teach the system over time. Multi-map systems such as in [11] utilized several different experiences of the given map and chose the most appropriately taught path for given conditions [12]. Newer works switch between the maps based on the appearance and the particle filtering for image association [13]. Another approach was to modify the feature maps of the environment, such as in [14], [15] where authors were replacing features with consequent traversals of the map, thus updating the map to the latest situation. In [16], [17], the authors took the idea further and based the feature visibility on temporal models; therefore, the repeated map was based on expected-to-be-seen features.

Early VTR approaches utilized handcrafted features [18], [19] that provide a shift between map image and camera feed. Newer approaches [20], [21], [22], [23] showed that trained feature extractors can be more stable than the handcrafted ones. Other systems use deep-learning [24] and bio-inspired [25] image processing to perform place recognition and estimate the heading or used convolutional neural networks to estimate the quality of heading correction [26]. With the assumption that the mobile robot moves only in local 2D space, the horizontal image displacement is the only important

measure [4]. This led to methods that would not be viable in 3D, such as cross-correlation of sub-sampled images [25], and later to encoding image by the neural network before cross-correlation [24]. Neural networks, however, require a large enough dataset to be trained on.

Annotation of such datasets can be a major bottleneck. This was addressed in [27] where authors used inputs such as GPS and kinematic constraints [28] to support self-annotation. Self-supervised reinforcement learning is typically performed in simulation, to train reactive navigation algorithms [29]. However, it might suffer from transfer onto real-life robots due to Sim-to-Real gap. In [30], authors train on the real platform, but the work is focused mostly on obstacle avoidance.

The authors of [31] proposed the use of handcrafted features during routine robot operation to annotate visual data needed to train a neural network. The output of the network was fused with the features-based method, resulting in a navigation system, capable of continuous improvement through self-supervised learning. This approach, however, still requires automated collection and selection of the data to be tough on. To ensure that the system is provided with data of sufficient quality, the robot has to actively explore the environment to gather them. The exploration process should produce balanced dataset reflecting the diversity of the operational environment.

This is analogous to active learning approaches, which select training data from larger datasets [32]. However, unlike in active learning, where the constraint is typically tied with annotation efforts, our system has to deal with limited time budget to gather the data. This means that the robot has to decide where to navigate to obtain data during allotted times, leading to approaches analogous to spatio-temporal exploration [33]. In contrast to these approaches [33], [34], we do not attempt to construct high fidelity environment maps, but focus on training a neural model for Visual Teach and Repeat.

Article	Navigation	Model learning		Active exploration
		Batch	Continuous	
[5], [6], [7], [4]	●	○	○	○
[35], [10], [24], [22]	●	●	○	○
[13], [30], [31], [11]	●	●	◐	○
[33], [34], [36]	○	●	●	●
Ours	●	●	●	●

Table I: Overview of navigation approaches in long-term scenarios.

III. METHOD DESCRIPTION

Our goal is to enable VTR navigation to improve itself over time and direct its data gathering when introduced to new scenarios. To achieve it, we employ concepts from mobile robotic exploration and long-term mapping such as place prioritization, entropy-based exploration or exploration ratio [34], [37], [36].

The visual teach and repeat pipeline is based on camera data to correct the robot's heading during its repeat mission to steer it to the intended path. We assume the robot was taught how to traverse the path by a human operator beforehand and collected images indexed by the traveled distance either by odometry or dead-reckoning. Based on [5], [4], repeating taught polygonal

or smooth paths does not require full 6DOF localization. The robot can instead estimate its heading based on a comparison of stored and current images and correct its heading accordingly via the visual servoing rule. The heading correction to keep on the desired path can be calculated as a horizontal displacement between the images. The displacement can be calculated by matching point features or neural network-based image registration. Combining the feature and network-based approaches [31] showed that the neural network can be trained using alignments from original feature matching systems. This allows the network to be trained and improved over the long term without any human intervention. This system is able to improve the robot's performance over time by gaining more information and learning about the environment. This scheme is called Visual Teach, Repeat and Learn (VTRL).

The core of our system (Fig. 2) is based on this self-supervised feature matching pipeline (VTRL) as a basis for continuous long-term improvement. The proposed pipeline receives data limited by the maximum daily operational time to teach the VTRL. Then, the evaluation part of the VTRL is used to estimate which images used for the training are tough based on VTRL image registration ambiguity. Based on some metadata of the images, such as specific place where was image taken it groups the images into **groups** g . It calculates the **ambiguity** of all images in a group where **preferences** \mathbf{p} are made. It then uses the \mathbf{p} to make a new **timetable** \mathbf{T} for the next iteration of data that it wants to observe within the given time constraints. This is then repeated for the next **iteration** i . The goal is to obtain the best **weights** \mathbf{W} for the neural network of the VTRL to align the robot most robustly and precisely using a limited amount of time dedicated to training data gathering.

A. System overview

Each pipeline run is called a mission, which encapsulates the initial conditions of the run, such as uptime, initial time table and other parameters (described below). Each mission has several iterations i where the pipeline decides what information it wants to get next. Each iteration uses given \mathbf{p} that is then used by scheduler to create new \mathbf{T} based on internal parameters, and then the requested images by \mathbf{T} are given to the pipeline while using datasets or obtained by the robot by using learned VTRL to navigate to the given places. In real-life deployments, not all requested data are obtainable due to unforeseen circumstances, such as some places not being accessible. In our dataset, some information is missing which in turn simulates real-life deployment. All gathered images are then passed to VTRL for the next round of training. The VTRL outputs **likelihood** ℓ of horizontal shift for the available image pairs from the same place. This is then used to calculate ambiguity \mathbf{a} . The ambiguity is then used to compute new \mathbf{p} and therefore \mathbf{T} for the next iteration.

The pipeline consists of 4 main parts:

- 1) New Mission module that encapsulates all parameters (initial, \mathbf{p} , past \mathbf{T} etc.) and makes strategy and time table which information should be obtained.
- 2) Original VTRL system. Takes a timetable and obtains a list of images either from a real robot or dataset. It

Figure 2: System data flow. The adaptive pipeline runs until there is no new data to be acquired. Evaluation can be run at the end or during every iteration of the adaptive pipeline, as well as for robot navigation if the input is a map. The new addition compared to VTRL is highlighted in **bold**.

then uses those images to train on and improve weights (\mathbf{W}_{init}) and computes the likelihood for all encountered image pairs for the preference module.

- 3) New Preferences module. Receives a list of likelihoods and computes ambiguity for each group to acquire preferences for the next iteration.
- 4) New Grading module. Generates multiple missions with different initial arguments and then takes ground truth to compare it against the mission results. It is used for VTRL introspection and experiment evaluation.

B. Mission

The mission module has several initial parameters, enabling it to generate strategies for each iteration i . Each strategy is generated based on the initial parameters of the mission past strategy, and given \mathbf{p} that is initially uniform for all watched parameters. Parameters relevant to this study are:

"Uptime", which states the percentage of the allotted time window, can be used to gain more information. For example, 50% allows to use only half of the time slots per day. This corresponds to the upper limit of current robots that are supposed to operate without any human interaction.

"Duty cycle", dc , dictates percentage of places/images that can be visited each time the robot tries to gain information. For example, 50% means the robot can visit approximately half the places during the given time slot. It simulates the effect of

real-world tasks, which constrain the robot from reaching all places during one time slot.

"Exploration exploitation ratio" $eeratio$ defines how much time a robot can dedicate from uptime to exploration and exploitation. The exploitation is part of a mission where the robot does not have a choice of what images will be presented to it. This is, however, still operational time; therefore, the robot should be able to collect data presented during this part of the task. In exploration, the robot uses \mathbf{p} to decide which information is more desirable for its learning.

"Explorations" dictate how the system selects places to visit the next time it can decide. With three different approaches each having effect on preferences for the next iteration: 1) **random** selects random \mathbf{p} , 2) **static** selects \mathbf{p} uniformly over all groups, 3) **adaptive** selects \mathbf{p} depending on past ambiguity.

"Preferences" \mathbf{p} gives ratios between all information groups \mathbf{g} by which the \mathbf{T} is generated. For example, $[1, 0.5, 0.33]$, the robot will try to go twice as often to images with groups 1, then 2 and thrice for 1, then 3. All initial \mathbf{p} are uniform for the first run, making all places equally important.

Each strategy then generates a timetable \mathbf{T} that it wants to visit where \mathbf{T}_{new} is a $M \times N$ matrix of M possible places and N possible times.

Two more parameters that do not directly influence the timetable making but rather how the pipeline is structured are:

"Preteach" allows the pipeline to use weights for training obtained from previous iterations so $\mathbf{W}_{init} = \mathbf{W}_{i-1}$. Otherwise, all training is done from initial randomized weights.

"Roll data" forces the pipeline to disregard any data not from its current iteration of the timetable. Otherwise it is going to use $\mathbf{T}_i = \mathbf{T}_{new} + \mathbf{T}_{i-1}$.

Both are implemented mainly for comparison to the old system with their interaction described in Algorithm:1.

All those parameters are used to generate new \mathbf{T}_i , which is then used to get a list of images $list_i$ by either lookup in a dataset or robots traversal of the request places. This $list_i$ is then given to the original VTRL system to learn on.

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Data:  $\mathbf{W}_0, \mathbf{p}_0, D_{0..n}$ 
 $i, \mathbf{W}_i, \mathbf{p}_i \leftarrow 0, \mathbf{W}_0, \mathbf{p}_0;$ 
while  $i < n$  do
  if roll data then
     $\mathbf{T}_i \leftarrow \text{compute } T_i(\mathbf{p}_i);$ 
  else
     $\mathbf{T}_i \leftarrow \text{compute } T_i(\mathbf{p}_i, \mathbf{T}_{i-1});$ 
     $list_i \leftarrow \text{runrobot}(\mathbf{T}_i)/\text{polldataset}(\mathbf{T}_i, D_i);$ 
  if preteach then
     $\mathbf{W}_i \leftarrow VTRL_{learn}(list_i, \mathbf{W}_{i-1}, \mathbf{W}_{i-1});$ 
  else
     $\mathbf{W}_i \leftarrow VTRL_{learn}(list_i, \mathbf{W}_{i-1}, \mathbf{W}_0);$ 
     $l_i \leftarrow VTRL_{eval}(list_i, \mathbf{W}_i);$ 
     $\mathbf{a}_i \leftarrow \text{ambiguity}(list_i, l_i);$ 
     $\mathbf{p}_{i+1}, i \leftarrow \mathbf{p}_i(\mathbf{a}_i), i + 1;$ 
end
Output:  $\mathbf{W}_{0..n}, \mathbf{p}_{0..n}, list_{0..n}$ 

```

Algorithm 1: Teaching algorithm

C. VTRL

The original system receives $list_i$, annotates them using \mathbf{W}_{i-1} (if exists) and uses them for self-learning. The system is in better detail described in [31] with some improvements taken from [13]. Changes were performed to achieve full compatibility with the open-source system [13] by unifying the dimensions of the internal representations. To make the system agnostic to image sizes, all displacements are represented as percentages of image width instead of an absolute number of pixels. This allows the use of datasets with differently sized images, improving the reproducibility of the research presented. Implementing the VTRL system as a Python library simplifies its integration, allowing easier reproduction of the experiments. While the feature-matching part of VTRL uses the full resolution of the received image, we convert all the images to 512×348 px before passing it to neural network.

The learning uses \mathbf{W}_{init} with annotated pairs of images and produces new weights \mathbf{W}_i . It then again takes $list_i$ and evaluates it using its newly trained weights \mathbf{W}_i , which returns a list of likelihoods l_i for each image pair used for introspection of the network and generation of ambiguity.

D. Preferences

Preference is a main output of the pipeline which dictates the ratios places should be visited in the next iteration. This module uses $list_i$ and l_i to compute ambiguity and generate preferences \mathbf{p}_i . For each image, an ambiguity a is computed using one of three different metrics:

The first is the sum of e_ℓ , denoted as $a_{entropy}$. It was used as an indicator if the pure entropy is a sufficiently good indicator for preferences. It showed strong preferences for places that were visited often even though they had small entropy.

The second is created by computing entropy e_ℓ for each likelihood and thresholding it by mean \bar{e} of all likelihoods with standard deviation with parameter θ producing $a_{threshold}$. This prevents numerical instability when adding together large amounts of small entropies as in $a_{entropy}$. Instead of the static threshold, we chose $\theta = 10$ as it guarantees that some information will propagate through.

The third compute ratio between the second highest and highest peak of the likelihood produces a_{ratio} .

The use of a_{ratio} was inspired by the inner mechanics of the VTRL system that uses this ratio to decide if the learning candidate will be used in training.

$$a_{entropy} = \sum_{e_\ell} e_\ell \quad (1)$$

$$a_{threshold} = \sum_{e_\ell} \llbracket e_\ell > (\bar{e} + \frac{\sigma_e}{\theta}) \rrbracket \quad (2)$$

$$a_{ratio} = \sum_{l_i} \frac{\max_2 l_i}{\max_1 l_i} \quad (3)$$

Images are then grouped by places, and each group \mathbf{g} has the ambiguity score calculated by adding over all images within

the group divided by image count for each group to get \mathbf{a} for each group

$$\mathbf{a} = \sum_{place} \frac{a_g}{|g_{place}|}. \quad (4)$$

This is then used to compute new \mathbf{p} , such as

$$\mathbf{p}_i = \mathbf{p}_{i-1} \cdot \mathbf{a} \quad (5)$$

if the adaptive exploration is selected. Otherwise, it is either random or static. It is then checked to satisfy the maximum limit by duty cycle by

$$\mathbf{p}_i = \frac{\mathbf{p}_i \cdot dc}{\sum_i \mathbf{p}_i}. \quad (6)$$

This can result in preferences larger than 1 for some groups. Therefore, it is then capped to one, redistributing the reminder evenly to others to preserve the duty cycle. This method also forbids the pipeline from over-focusing on one specific group if the duty cycle allows it.

E. Grading

This module serves only evaluation purposes for introspection into the pipeline and is used for robot navigation. It takes the latest \mathbf{W}_i from the teaching algorithm and does a forward pass using VTRL with those weights, producing correction displacements for the robot. If ground truth is present, it is compared to these displacements to produce system error for each image. It computes the accuracy curve (described below) for each M for future introspection.

IV. EXPERIMENTS

Datasets used for this pipeline are required to have enough passes of the same places. We used the Witham Wharf [38] dataset comprised of 7+3 days of robot traversing indoor office space in Lincoln University, taking pictures of 8 places every 10 minutes, resulting in $\sim 1000 \times 8$ images. The first 7 days, collected all at once, were used for training. The other 3 days, collected a week, a month and a year after the initial set, were used for validation and as a ground truth for our methods.

Figure 3: All eight locations. Starting from top left are: office 1, office 2, office 3, kitchen. Continuing on the second line: windows entrance, windows sofas, windows 1, windows 2. The original dataset was gathered in that order. Groups are based on [34], [39] and outdoor/indoor illumination prevalence.

Second dataset Čestlice was used for training was based on photos taken on a large outdoor parking lot of a local strip mall where 31 passes were made over 272 positions resulting

Figure 4: Average preferences with standard deviations for each location over a week of operation. Examples of locations are presented in Fig. 3

in $\sim 31 \times 272$ images. [40]. This dataset size is similar to the Witham Wharf; however, the time-to-location ratio differs.

Results are presented using the same metrics as in [16], [26], [24] except image percentage error is computed instead of pixel error. This is done for the sole reason that images have different widths in all data. All previous works used the accuracy curve (AC) to visualize results from one run. Since we wanted more accurate results, we added a mean and boundaries of all runs for a given parameter where applicable. Simplification of the results was necessary to perform correlation between parameters. The integral of the AC provided a number representing the performance of a model and its the teaching method. The higher the integral value, the better the system performs. It should be noted that the maximum of the integral is 0.5, while the system correctly estimates all shifts with pixel accuracy. The contrary minimum should be 0.25, where the system randomly guesses the results.

Default values for the pipeline, unless mentioned otherwise, are Exploration/exploitation ratio: 1, Preteach: True, Roll data: False and as Entropy threshold metric. Moreover, both datasets have different Uptime and Duty cycle of 0.5 for Wharf and 0.75 for Čestlice. This has been done to mitigate shorter time-span of the Čestlice dataset. All results are presented as box plots with charted averages, upper/lower quartiles and outliers of the integrals obtained from multiple runs of the given sets of parameters to reduce the effect of randomness on the results.

A. Location preference vs. similarity

First, we focus on the progression of preferences over time since it allows us to see if the robot is consistently going for the same data. From all the eight possible locations present in the dataset, not all have the same frequency, and some might be considered more similar than others as seen in Figure 3. The original dataset contains places with similar information, such as office1, office2 and office3. On the other hand, some other places, such as kitchen or sofas, are less similar since they have features or whole scene structures unique to the whole

dataset. For comparison, the preferences for each place are presented with their evolution over iterations/time in Figure 4.

B. Comparison to previous work

Since the system builds on previous self-learning work VTRL [31] where there was no addition of newly acquired data, we compare it to the original system. The original system behaved the same way as if the roll data parameter was true and the change rate was static. This means that no past data are used during each round of teaching and that there are no changes in the strategy after the initial run. Additionally, the original paper explores how the system behaves when only the initial weights are used as the basis for learning, albeit it showed that continuous teaching was superior. To confirm past work parameter preteach is also studied in this part. While not used in this exploration/exploitation ratio, which was set to pure exploration, it is still represented in its extreme here, where the random change is a scenario where robots are always told where to go, comparing systems where the robot has no chance to explore at all.

C. Duty cycle and Uptime

The parameters Duty cycle dc and Uptime affect how many places the robot can visit for each run during the mission. Both range from 0 to 100% where the dc dictates the percentage of accessible places and the other percentage of available time windows to be used. Duty cycle of 100% gives all information available to the robot; therefore all methods should perform the same since there is no choice. For other circumstances, the less information the robot is capable of gathering, the more it needs to select it intelligently. Different sizes of used datasets (1007x8 and 30x271) showed different requirements for combining these parameters due to a need to form learning pairs, as seen in Figure. 5. The uptime-affected dimension of the datasets scales exponentially due to combinatorics compared to the dc dimension, which scales linearly.

Figure 5: Plot of relative performance for different percentages of Duty cycle and Uptime per dataset. Missing values (white space) did not learn at all due to lack of training pairs. Note the different absolute values of used slots for each dataset.

D. Exploration exploitation

In a typical operation, a robot has to fulfil its task compared to only exploration. This is represented by the exploration/exploitation ratio, which dictates during how many

Figure 6: Box plots of integrals obtained from the final iteration of learning (higher is better). The no-change continued weights represent the original system. The random change represents a run where the robot does not explore at all and only uses data gathered during its mission execution

available time slots the robot can choose which places to visit. If this ratio is zero, then the robot has no choice in what to see, contrary to one when the robot only explores. To the exploration, the exploitation step acts as annealing since it forces the robot to go to places it might have already deemed well understood.

E. Hardware requirements

The training was performed using an RTX3080 graphics card and AMD 3950X CPU, where each image pair took, on average, 34 ms. Total training time depends on total image pairs received, which varies widely depending mainly on duty cycle, uptime and roll data. With roll data functionally capping the maximum number of image pairs per iteration the system can receive, limiting the maximum train time per iteration. This currently limits the learning time to about 200 seconds per iteration but decreases the system performance significantly as visible in Figure 6. With the roll data set to false, the time needed for training grows exponentially with each iteration. Eventually, the required training time will exceed the robot's idle time. The roll data parameter prevents this situation when set to *True* as it limits the amount of training data.

F. Ablation and Results

Figures 6, 7 and 8 explore parameter influences for both datasets. In Table II we present an ablation study as well as parameter influence. The pipeline performs and improves as expected on the Witham Wharf dataset, where adding either random or adaptive exploration works. The Čestlice dataset ranks similarly, but the difference between Static and Adaptive approaches is not statistically significant. The cause of this might be a different size of the datasets that has large amount of places to visit mostly due requirement to obtain training pairs. These pairs are created more often if there is larger

Figure 7: Integrals obtained from the final iteration of learning. Different results of exploration/exploitation ratio.

Figure 8: Box plots of integrals obtained from the final learning iteration. Three metrics types as in Eq. (1) (2) (3).

amount of the same place images which is something the static and adaptive replicate but is not present in random.

All statistical tests to quantify the relative performance of different variants of our pipeline were done using the non-parametric Quade test [41] for complete block-design studies. Outcomes of each test were corrected for multiple comparisons by the Šidák correction [42] and performed at significance level $\alpha = 0.05$. In Table II, we show the resulting rankings for all tests and for each test p-values quantifying the difference in ordering between the two variants consecutive in the average rank. Note that all the tests were performed using different sets of samples of different sizes, as shown in the table.

G. Discussion

Preferences of the pipeline over time converge to a specific form, which prefers only specific locations as visible in Fig. 4. This shows that the network is able to identify the ratio of images it requires for the best learning. It effectively balances the datasets regarding information gain per group in contrast to the previous system, which was forced to use a static approach of images. Fig. 4 also shows dependence on proper group selection since some images could be grouped together. The group distinction is heavily dependent on the mission and the ability to provide proper data to the robot when requested. Allowing the robot to select more granular groups, such as the presence of windows or people, would result in overlapping

	Average Rank		<i>p</i> values	
	Wharf	Čestlice	Wharf	Čestlice
Deactivated (Fig. 2)			$n = 72$	$n = 78$
None	1.63	1.83		
Adaptive exploration	2.13	2.22	0.011	0.044
Scheduler	2.25	1.95	<0.001	0.998
Method			$n = 60$	$n = 102$
Entropy threshold	1.50	2.07		
Entropy	2.07	1.92	0.011	0.922
Ratio	2.43	2.01	0.011	0.816
Roll data			$n = 216$	$n = 180$
All data	1.12	1.49		
New data	1.88	1.51	<0.001	0.043
Preteach			$n = 216$	$n = 180$
Continued weights	1.13	1.34		
All weights	1.87	1.66	<0.001	<0.001

Table II: Average ordering (the smaller, the better) and the corresponding p-values. Significant results are in **bold**.

groups, which is out of the scope of this paper but, in theory, should improve its capability to properly select desired data.

As evident in Fig. 6, the new system outperforms the previous state of the art due to its ability to select proper data. This experiment confirms results from previous work, which suggests that the learning should continue on past weights and build on these as seen in Tab. II (Preteach). Moreover, we see that using all data compared to only the last iteration helps the pipeline as seen in Tab. II (Roll Data).

Multiple metrics for the adaptive approach were tested; they show in Fig. 8 that usage of mean and standard deviation of entropy outperforms all others for Witham Wharf. The ratio between the two highest peaks performs worse than the pure sum of entropy as visible in Tab. II. The Čestlice datasets trends are similar but are not statistically significant, which suggests that the metrics type is dependent on the environment more than we expected. In Witham Wharf, the difference between Entropy and Entropy Thresholded might be due to the accumulation of small values which are acceptable and omnipresent in the entropy of network output. In the entropy threshold metric, the θ allows it to weed out those small values and discern between sets with infrequent extremes and low uncertainties. More work, especially the parameter θ , should be tested since it was chosen to be static in this work for brevity. Some other introspection, like combining different metrics, such as first thresholding and then adding the entropy, might be beneficial in the future. Moreover, new methods that would improve performance on Čestlice should be tested.

For actual deployment, it is best if the robot can visit all places; therefore, it does not need any adaptive information since it sees all places which corresponds to 100% duty cycle.

These parameters are fully dependent on the given mission and capabilities of the robot. It shows that any deployment should strive for as much time as possible so that the robot can complete its mission with no downtime. From Figure 5, we can deduce that the relative performance rises more with Uptime in the Čestlice dataset than in Witham Wharf. This is caused by the asymmetric nature of the dataset, where the chance of getting an image pair is much lower when a larger time slot selection is available. To improve more, the robot could choose not only places where to go but also times when

it departs on the mission. This might be addressed in future work by exploring periodicity and/or other time phenomena.

Regarding exploration versus exploitation, the performance improves with higher exploration and lower exploitation. The robot then performs best when it has total freedom where to go and observe its environment corresponding to $eeratio = 1$. Our experiments show significantly better results with increasing exploration for Witham Wharf (T-test for presence of trend, $\beta = 0.003$, $p = 0.007$, $n = 210$) and for Čestlice ($\beta = 0.004$, $p = 0.033$, $n = 354$); see Fig. 7. However, we have observed situations where robots decided not to explore one place anymore in pure exploration mode since it has already assessed the place is already well known. A problem of blind spots can also accompany this if the robot never visits a specific place; it does not know it exists. The exploitation acts as an annealing to the original searched space of unknown information. The $eeratio$ depends on the environment and the robot's mission and might even change over the course of a given mission. If features in the environment are static or with small enough volatility, the system might need to explore only at the start of the mission and gradually decrease this parameter. Conversely, if a large change is detected or the environment is known to undergo fast changes, the exploration should bring better results.

V. CONCLUSION

We presented an extension to the learning platform VTRL that is able to choose better training data according to its belief in data ambiguity. We extended the original VTRL by implementing a pipeline allowing a robot to provide preferences on which information it wants to acquire. This allows a real robot to continuously improve its ability to repeat the paths it has been taught before in an efficient manner. The functionality of the pipeline is presented using datasets collected by real robots. We have tested several metrics for the ambiguity, which yielded the best approach to be expanded upon in future works.

The system can balance information in the provided data, and it might be possible to select the groups dynamically. In the future, we will consider the temporal dimension, i.e., plan not only where but also when to gather additional information.

For the sake of research reproducibility, we provide codes and data publicly at: <https://github.com/rouceto1/vtrl>.

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